

Studies on Benzenesulphonamidomethyl Benzimidazoles. Part V. Formation Constants of Copper(II) Chelates of α -Benzenesulphonamido γ -2-Benzimidazolyl *n*-Butyramide

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A potentiometric study on the complex formation of Cu(II) with α -benzenesulphonamido γ -2-benzimidazolyl *n*-butyramide (RH₂) in (1:1) water-dioxan at a constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.5$) at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$, has indicated the formation of two complexes, Cu(RH)⁺ and Cu(RH)₂⁰. The successive formation constants (K₁ & K₂) have been determined following the method of Irving and Rossotti. Log K₁ and log K₂ are computed by graphical methods and found to be 8.28 ± 0.03 and 5.12 ± 0.03 respectively. At the later stages of titration the complex Cu(RH)₂⁰ undergoes two steps of acid dissociation for which pk_2 and pk_1 values are found to be 9.16 ± 0.03 and 9.20 ± 0.03 respectively. Two acid dissociation constants (k_2^* & k_1^*) of the species RH₃⁺ have also been determined under identical conditions, and pk_2^* and pk_1^* values are found to be 5.37 ± 0.02 and 10.75 ± 0.02 respectively.

SOME biologically important chelating agents containing both sulphonamido group and benzimidazole nucleus are reported earlier from this laboratory^{1,2}. The present paper describes the formation of Cu(II) chelates of another such compound³ namely α -benzenesulphonamido γ -2-benzimidazolyl *n*-butyramide (RH₂).

Acid dissociation constants (k_2^* & k_1^*) of the protonated species RH₃⁺ and formation constants (K₁ & K₂) of its Cu(II) chelates Cu(RH)⁺ and Cu(RH)₂⁰ have been potentiometrically determined following Irving and Rossotti titration technique⁴ and acid dissociation constants (k_2 and k_1) of the complex Cu(RH)₂⁰ following Bjerrum-Calvin *pH*-titration technique^{5,6} in (1:1) water-dioxan at $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$ in presence of requisite amount of sodium perchlorate to maintain ionic strength constant ($\mu=0.5$).

Experimental

Materials and Methods: The ligand RH₂ was prepared by treating the condensation product of *N*-benzenesulphonyl L(+) glutamic acid and *o*-phenylene diamine, with thionyl chloride followed by ammonia³. It was recrystallized from warm aqueous DMSO and air dried, m. p. 210° (dec.). All other reagents were either of A. R. quality or properly purified. Their solutions were made in double distilled CO₂-free water and purified dioxan⁷.

pH measurements were made with a Cambridge portable type *pH*-meter using a glass electrode of 1–13 *pH* range in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode connected by means of an agar–2*M* NaNO₃ bridge. The *pH*-meter was calibrated with sodium hydrogen phthalate and borax buffer solutions in water with due temperature corrections.

Potentiometric titrations of 50 ml portions in (1:1) water-dioxan of the following mixtures—(A) 0.01*M* HClO₄; (B) 0.01*M* HClO₄ + 0.02*M* RH₃ClO₄; (C) or (D) 0.01*M* HClO₄ + 0.02*M* RH₃ClO₄ + 0.005*M* or 0.0075*M* Cu(ClO₄)₂ with a 0.1424*M* NaOH solution in (1:1) water-dioxan, were carried out at $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. Ionic strength of the media was kept constant ($\mu=0.5$) throughout by adding requisite amount of NaClO₄. Duplicate titrations were made in each case under identical conditions. Titration curves—*pH* vs volume of alkali solution added, were plotted.

Results

The acid dissociation of the protonated species RH₃⁺ may be represented as stated below:

From the titration curves, the average number of protons (\bar{n}_H) associated with the ion RH⁻, have been calculated using the relation of Irving and Rossotti⁴. The evaluation of pk_2^* and pk_1^* have been made by linear plots on the assumption that [RH⁻] ≈ 0 when $2 > \bar{n}_H > 1$ and [RH₃⁺] ≈ 0 when $0 < \bar{n}_H < 1$.

The \bar{n}_H values have also been calculated using the experimentally determined values of k_2^* and k_1^* . The standard deviation (σ) has been calculated⁹ using the relation (3)

$$\sigma = \pm \frac{([\bar{n}_H(\text{calc.}) - \bar{n}_H(\text{expt.})]^2 / \text{Number of observations})^{1/2}}{\dots} \quad (3)$$

The limits of error of the constants are obtained from the maximum horizontal displacements of the calculated curves ($\bar{n}_H(\text{calc.})$ vs pH) from the experimental ones⁹. Results are stated in Table 1.

Acid dissociation constants of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2^0$: When $\bar{n} \approx 2$, the acid dissociation of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2^0$ begins in a stepwise manner as represented below

Now at any stage of titration the following relations will hold good after the attainment of equilibrium

$$\text{M} = \text{M}_2 + \text{M}' + \text{M}'' \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

$$\text{R} = \text{R}_3 + \text{R}_2 + \text{R}_1 + 2\text{M} \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Cu(II) CHELATES AND ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF RH_3^+ AND $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2^0$

Species	pK_2^*	pK_1^*	$\log k_1$	$\log k_2$	pK_3	pK_1
RH_3^+	5.37 ± 0.02	10.75 ± 0.02
Cu(II) chelates	8.28 ± 0.03	5.12 ± 0.03
$\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2^0$	9.16 ± 0.03	9.20 ± 0.03
	± 0.007	$(0 < \bar{n}_H < 2)^*$	± 0.011	$(0 < \bar{n} < 1.70)^*$	± 0.012	$(0.45 < \bar{n}_H^1 < 1.70)^*$

* Standard deviation (σ)

Formation constants of $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})^+$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2^0$: The stepwise formation of Cu(II) complex with the protonated species RH_3^+ may be represented as

It is assumed that the acid dissociation of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2^0$ is negligible at the time of complex formation steps (4) and (5). From the titration curves, the average number (\bar{n}) of ligand (RH^-) bound to Cu(II) and free ligand exponent pL ($L = [\text{RH}^-]$) using the relations of Irving and Rossotti⁴.

On plotting \bar{n} vs. pL , one may obtain formation curve and the successive formation constants K_1 and K_2 have been evaluated by linear plot of the equation (6)

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(2 - \bar{n})L^2} = \frac{(1 - \bar{n})}{(2 - \bar{n})L} \times K_1 + K_1 K_2 \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

The \bar{n} values have been calculated, using experimentally determined values of K_1 and K_2 , and the calculated formation curve has been drawn along with the experimental points. Standard deviation and limits of error have also been determined. Results are stated in Table 1. The experimental points are in good agreement with the calculated curve upto $\bar{n} = 1.70$. Deviation of the experimental points from the calculated curve when $\bar{n} > 1.70$ indicates that the course of reaction step at the later stages of complex formation is accompanied by the simultaneous acid dissociation of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2^0$.

and as the solutions are electrically neutral

$$\text{P} + \text{H}^+ + \text{R}_3 = 2\text{M} + \text{F} + \text{OH}^- + \text{R}_1 + \text{M}' + 2\text{M}'' + \text{R} \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

where M, R, F and P are the initial concentrations of Cu^{2+} , RH_3^+ , free HClO_4 and alkali respectively, and M_2 , M' , M'' , R_3 , R_2 , R_1 , H^+ and OH^- are equilibrium concentrations of $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2^0$, $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})(\text{R})^-$, $\text{Cu}(\text{R})_2^{2-}$, RH_3^+ , RH_2 , RH^- , acid and alkali respectively. In order to determine equilibrium concentrations of acid and alkali, a graphical method was employed¹⁰.

The average number (\bar{n}_H) of the protons bound to the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{R})_2^{2-}$ ion is given by the relation

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{2\text{M}_2 + \text{M}'}{\text{M}_2 + \text{M}' + \text{M}''} \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

One may now deduce from equations (9–12)

$$\bar{n}_H = 4 - \frac{1}{M} (\text{P} + \text{H}^+ - \text{F} - \text{OH}^- - \text{R}) + \frac{(\text{R} - 2\text{M}) \left(\frac{k_1^*}{[\text{H}^+]} - \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2^*} \right)}{M \left(\frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2^*} + 1 + \frac{k_1^*}{[\text{H}^+]} \right)} \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

\bar{n}_H values are plotted against pH (Fig. 1) and the successive dissociation constants k_2 and k_1 have been evaluated by linear plot of the equation (14)

$$\frac{(2 - \bar{n}_H) [\text{H}^+]^2}{\bar{n}_H} = \frac{k_2 (\bar{n}_H - 1) [\text{H}^+]}{\bar{n}_H} + k_1 k_2 \quad (14)$$

which may be deduced from the equation (12). Calculated \bar{n}_H values have been obtained employing experimentally determined values of k_2 and k_1 . The calculated curve has been drawn along with the experimental points (Fig. 1). Standard deviation and the limits of error have also been determined following usual procedure and results are stated in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Acid dissociation curve of $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2^0$: 0.005M Cu(II), O; 0.0075M Cu(II), Δ ; calculated curve using $\text{p}K_2^* = 9.16$ and $\text{p}K_1^* = 9.20$. ———.

Discussion

The method of Irving and Rossotti has been employed to determine the dissociation constants k_2^* and k_1^* of the ligand RH_3^+ and the formation constants K_1 and K_2 of its Cu(II) complexes. The $\text{p}K_2^*$ and $\text{p}K_1^*$ values are found to be 5.37 and 10.75 respectively of which the first one is obviously due to deprotonation of benzimidazolium ion and the second is due to dissociation of imidohydrogen of $-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}-$ group¹¹.

The study indicates that RH_3^+ may act as a biprotic tridentate ligand at the early stages of complex formation with Cu(II). The standard deviation was found to be ± 0.011 in the region $0 < \bar{n} < 1.70$. The deviation of the experimental points from the calculated curve at $\bar{n} > 1.70$ may be due to the commencement of acid dissociation of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2^0$. The dissociation is also indicated by the colour of the solution being changed from blue to pink at the later stages of titration. So it appears that the pink colouration is due to the formation of the anion $\text{Cu}(\text{R})_2^{2-}$. It has also been followed potentiometrically and the dissociation constants k_2 and k_1 have also been determined. The

standard deviation has been found to be ± 0.012 in the region $0.45 < \bar{n}_H < 1.70$. The deviation at $\bar{n}_H > 1.70$ may be due to overlapping of the complex formation step and at $\bar{n}_H < 0.45$ is probably due to decomposition to hydroxo-complexes. Although the proton dissociation of RH^- to R^{2-} (i. e. $-\text{CONH}_2$ to $-\text{CONH}^-$) could not be detected during titration even at $\text{pH} \approx 12.5$, it is well known that such dissociation may take place at lower pH values due to coordination of nitrogen of $-\text{CONH}_2$ group to a metal ion. The proton of $-\text{CONH}_2$ group becomes more acidic on the formation of metal-nitrogen bond. The enhancement of acidity appears to be a direct function of metal nitrogen bond strength^{12,13}.

Possibilities of the formation of polynuclear species have been checked using two different concentrations (0.005M and 0.0075M) of Cu(II) with the same concentrations (0.02M) of RH_3^+ . The coincidence of the experimental points on the same curve supports the formation of mononuclear species such as $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})^+$, $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2^0$, $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})(\text{R})^-$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{R})_2^{2-}$. So at the later stages of complex formation with Cu(II), RH_3^+ appears to act as a triprotic tridentate one. With Ni(II) and Co(II), similar potentiometric studies were made, but no satisfactory proof of complex formation with RH_3^+ , was obtained.

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